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The Role of Video Games on Childhood Studying

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ABSTRACT

The most common and tolerable form of entertainment these days are ongoing demand of playing Video games. The numbers of grown-ups who play video games have augmented due to the earlier generation of gamers having transitioned or moved into adulthood. Although it is assumed that video games are mainly for children and is considered as “childish” or “juvenile,” the gaming industry has already stretched its height among the adult spectators. Many people working in the field of education, especially teachers of, as they say, the old in schools, one of the principal’s reactions especially pointed out: during the discussion on Permission to conduct student polling, the principal asked about the theme of the paper, and her reaction to the title role of video games in the student’s overall success was: “Oh, yes, that’s a very big problem.” We notice negative impression in older population, but since video games are so popular that sometimes they are considered a kind of art, they indubitably affect the lives of consumers, either positively or negatively. But how do video games affect students? It is indubitable that most children and adolescents at least sometimes play video games. For this reason, since the 1980s studies have been carried out on the subject of video games, mostly focused on negative impacts, especially the impact of violent video games, but certain positive impacts were also found. Some of the negative and positive impacts, found by previous research, are presented in this paper. These studies leave space for various interpretations, and therefore the main issues of these studies are also briefly presented in the paper. In order to understand the role of video games, as well as the results of the earliest research on the role of video games, we will briefly present the history of video games. But the

matter of children playing video games continues nowadays a lot. Many a times, games are attributed and accused for the escalation of violence and aggression among children. People have been inquisitive as to what the special effects of games on youngsters really are if whether they both have positive and negative effects or none at all. This study investigates into the behavior pattern of video game playing children and adolescents. Furthermore, it also examines their motivation for video games through a structured questionnaire. The study focuses on the demographic video game usage and preferences. It also studies whether such games lead to aggressive behavior or pro social behavior among the video game players. This study was conducted for 100 children and adolescent people playing such video games from various socio-economic backgrounds in Mumbai city. The type of sampling technique used is Simple Random Sampling wherein a questionnaire was prepared and circulated to the videogame players and as per the interpretation findings and conclusion were sought. The age of technological advancement has led to the rise of many things that children and adults can do on phones and computers. In the gone eras, children would congregate together and play ball games, athletics, or other games that involved physical interactions. The modern era has led to the current phenomenon where Children are locked up in houses, with little chance of knowing their next-door neighbors. With such a turn of events, leisure times are used either connecting with friends using social media platforms or playing virtual games such as FIFA and Need for Speed (NFS). The virtual games have created a distance between the Thinking capabilities and development of children in the modern era and in the past times. Video games have educational impacts as well as some negative effects on the growth and development of the child. The games may influence their ability to interact in real life, either positively or negatively. Not only do video games affect the ability of a child to cope socially and physically, but they also lead to both positive and negative long-term effects in their development.

Keywords: Video games, Child, Adult, Violence, Aggression, Behaviour

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays our students have a lot of for the extra activities and they are almost spending their precious time on the mobile as well as them almost wasting their time in video games. They have not trying to connect their studies with the books most of the time; they are in before Facebook or YouTube and other video games. In this case so many students learn good things as well as bad things almost our children open the prohibited sides. They have spent most of their time on the video games these also put the date on the learners learning.

TV, computers, the Internet, videogames (Play station, Game boy, BSB, etc.) have become a major challenge for parents and Muslim families in the contemporary world. Parents are wondering how to train their children. How to protect children from the negative effects of these things. It is fact that these things have positive and negative possessions found in the life of children. The positive and negative effects of video games are being observed. Family, society, the state and mankind will have to adopt a comprehensive and clear-cut approach to the future to tackle the problems and dangers of video games, without that it will not be built. The world of video games has had a wonderful revolution. The changes in skill have led to the realization of games, while there are many benefits to one side; many of the disadvantages have also emerged. Computer technology and the Internet have made video games for teens and children much cheaper and easier. Video games are affecting everyone.

As far as computer games and children are concerned, children are given similar training in these games. They also develop a desire to bleed and fulfill that desire. Logically, these exercises are nothing short of military exercises. Research has also shown that ordinary fighting games have a far worse effect than the worst kind of violence a movie can have on television or cinema. The reason is that when we are watching a movie, our character is limited to the viewing only, but when we sit in front of the computer and play the game we are part of the game. Especially in games where helmets and lenses are used, children are cut off from the outside world and become completely part of the game environment, then lose the game or In the event of winning, (Halvorsen, 2020).

They express the true emotions that are part of real life. Gradually, these unrealistic emotions become an integral part of real emotions and then these children remain as influential in real life and their reaction at the time also shows the dominant color of these emotions (Lee, Weeda, Insel, Somerville, Krabbendam, & Huizinga, 2018).

REASON STATEMENT

The main role of this Article to go through the relationship of video games at school levels understudies review point normal. Moreover, it expects to find the connection between computer games, time administration abilities, and study propensities.

LITERATURE REVIEW

At present, parents in countries not only in Pakistan but all over the world are worried about the child's obsession with electronic games and the resulting birth. The first computer game in the world was made in 1962 Krzywinska, (2018). Named Space War. Although the series of electronic games started at that time, the lack of access to everyone's computer did not make it public. This was reinforced when powerful personalcomputers began to become commonplace after the 1980s. After that, computer games also started to increase rapidly. Now the scope of these games has grown to such an extent that all the goose games, adventure games and action games are available at very cheap prices in the market (Groot, 2018).

It should be noted here that not all games have positive features. There are countless computer games in the market that show open common law violations. Their scenes are full of violence, and sexual offenses are portrayed in a very attractive way. Generally, the language used in these games is superficial and inferior, but it is also two hands ahead of the market language. The President of the American National Institute of Farmed or Family commented on it, saying, "Unfortunately, this has begun to be a catastrophic event that is morally destroying our new generation." 15 years of age According to one research, 80% of young people prefer playing games that are violent and based on different types of crime Reynolds, (2018). One psychologist commented on the situation, saying, "We just consider computer games to be a game, but unfortunately, it is taking our society in the wrong direction and we are giving our children all the things they need through computer games. Are causing them to have a negative impact on their future lives. A person who may not have learned to load a

weapon magazine for 60 years in real life but with the help of a computer he not only mastered the use of modern weapons, but at the same time was able to manipulate humans and other living things with bullets. He also learns" (Jhally, 1992).

HYPOTHESIS

H1: There is no significant role of computer game utilization on the student's outcomes.

H02. There is a significant role of computer game utilization on the student's outcomes.

METHODOLOGY

The current research study is descriptive investigation project. The measureable learning complicated the primary investigation that that engage and show the position as well as behaviour.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

To study the number of video game players among children and youth.

To study behavioural changes in the players due to video gaming.

To study role of video game on the players health.

To understand the effect of video games on the productivity of the player.

To know motivation factor among the players to play such games

VIDEO GAME PLAY MAY PROVIDE LEARNING, HEALTH, SOCIAL BENEFITS, REVIEW FINDS

Playing video games, including violent shooter games, may boost children's learning, health and social skills, according to a review of research in *American Psychologist*.

The study comes out as debate continues among psychologists and other health professionals regarding the effects of violent media on youth. An APA task force is conducting a comprehensive review of research on violence in video games and interactive media and will release its findings later this year. "Important research has already been conducted for decades on the negative effects of gaming, including addiction, depression and aggression, and we are certainly not suggesting that this should be ignored," says Isabela Granic, PhD, of Radboud University Nijmegen in The Netherlands, lead author of the article. "However, to understand the impact of video games on children's and adolescents' development, a more balanced

perspective is needed."While one widely held view maintains that playing video games is intellectually lazy, such play actually may strengthen a range of cognitive skills such as spatial navigation, reasoning, memory and perception, according to several studies reviewed in the article. This is particularly true for shooter video games, which are often violent, the authors found. A 2013 meta-analysis found that playing shooter video games improved a player's capacity to think about objects in three dimensions just as well as academic courses designed to enhance these same skills, according to the study."This has critical implications for education and career development, as previous research has established the power of spatial skills for achievement in science, technology, engineering and mathematics," Granic says. This enhanced thinking was not found when playing other types of video games, such as puzzles or role-playing games. Playing video games may also help children develop problem-solving skills, the authors said. The more adolescents reported playing strategic video games, such as role-playing games, the more they improved in problem solving and school grades the following year, according to a long-term study published in 2013. Children's creativity was also enhanced by playing any kind of video game, including violent games, but not when the children used other forms of technology, such as a computer or cell phone, other research revealed. Simple games that are easy to access and can be played quickly, such as "Angry Birds," can improve players' moods, promote relaxation and ward off anxiety, the study said. "If playing video games simply makes people happier, this seems to be a fundamental emotional benefit to consider," said Granic. The authors also highlighted the possibility that video games are effective tools for learning resilience in the face of failure.

By learning to cope with ongoing failures in games, the authors suggest that children build emotional resilience they can rely upon in their everyday lives. Another stereotype the research challenges is the socially isolated gamer. More than 70 percent of gamers play with a friend, and millions of people worldwide participate in massive virtual worlds through video games such as "Farmville" and "World of Warcraft," the article noted. Multiplayer games become virtual social communities, where decisions need to be made quickly about whom to trust or reject and how to lead a group, the authors said. People who play video games, even if they are violent, that encourage cooperation are more likely to be helpful to others while gaming than those who play the same games competitively, a 2011 study found.

ADVANTAGES

More acute thinking ability Playing video games affects the thinking of children because it causes them to be more calculative before they take any actions. They have a positive bearing on the basic mental processes such as decision-making, perception, memory, and attention. According to Gray (2015, p. 1), most video games require children to be focused on the virtual object with which they are playing[1].By keeping track of common mistakes that lead to the early termination of a game, a child can easily avoid some of the mistakes in the course of the game.

The games affect a child's decision-making process by requiring them to choose between several tools. For example in NFS, a child may be required to choose between several roads or even buy spares for their virtual vehicles. The ability to make the best choice will definitely have a bearing in the real life of a child. The perceptions of a child are augmented by the fact that video games require children to hold a lot of information in their mind. They are at liberty to decide which information to act upon first, or in what order (Gray, 2015, p.1) [1]. Gray further asserts that children who immerse themselves into active virtual gaming.

DISADVANTAGES

Lower grades

With all the benefits that video games have, they also have some negative roles to play in the development of children. Parents who allow their children to spend most of their leisure times playing video games report that the high-frequency results in poor performance in school Several studies have shown that the longer the time children spend playing games, the poorer they become in school.

A SHORT HISTORY OF VIDEO GAMES

The history of video games goes back to 1948, when the first electronic device for entertainment was designed (Kent, 2010). Over the next decade the development of video games accompanies computer development. The first commercial success of video games goes back to 1972, when the arcade game Pong, a table tennis simulation, emerged, followed by the development of arcade games such as pinball. Like other arcade games, Pong was located in public places, cafes, restaurants, and playrooms, and its popularity has stimulated tendency for video games in homes. Magnavox Odyssey, the first home game console, was released that year, which offered up to 28 different video games. Almost all the games on that console were sports or action genre. In 1977, as a result of the

development of the microprocessor, the Atari VCS (Atari 2600) game console appeared. The importance of such consoles was priceless. For the first time, video games, the goal of which was not simply to add balls or destroy opponents, but already require some strategic thinking, appeared. During the next year, the impact of video games on players has become a new research problem, especially with children and adolescents, who showed the most interest for the games. At the same time, the development of PCs had begun.

The number of computer users and consoles grew every year, and in the meantime, the number of home video game players exceeded the number of arcade video games in the public, which also influenced the greater isolation of people since the arcade video games were usually played in company. In 1984, Apple Macintosh, the first home computer with mouse and graphical interface appeared. This innovation further brought computers closer to the users, and consequently made video games even more accessible. The same innovation has had an impact on the scientific community since the first studies of video games and school success have been reported since 1985. These surveys raise questions about how long players were playing video games, and the average response amounts to 14 months or approximately since Apple Macintosh could be purchased (Burgess, 2012).

In the last decade of the 20th century, the greatest step in the quality of graphics and the complexity of the games was made. Following the gradual development of games from the previous decade, games that introduce a third dimension into the world of video games, making a stronger impression of reality and allowing stronger emotional connectivity with characters from video games. The popularization of 3D games has resulted in the emergence of action-packed First Person Shooter (FPS) video games, featuring explicit shootings and violence, which resulted in the Entertainment Software Rating Board, better known as ESRB, which prescribes the suitable age for certain game (Parks, 2012), or PEGI, Pan European Game Information, in Europe. Hardware of game consoles and computers is continually improving, enabling better graphics and more complex video games. In recent years we have witnessed the re-emergence of so-called virtual reality and popular VR glasses that give players the impression that they really are in the world of video games. Research a leading problem is how to explore the direct impact of video games on children and adults. No behavior can be attributed exclusively to video games because it is generally influenced by a number of factors. According to Nakaya (2015), under the influence of their own expectations, researchers often make different conclusions. For example, one can argue that video games are associated with

violence in schools, while others may argue that they are not closely related, with the same evidence that brought them to those opposite conclusions.

A specific example of the problem described is the interpretation of research where participants after playing violent video games showed a greater tendency to aggressive behaviour, such as releasing loud noises to other people. Anderson and Bushman (2001) believe that such behaviour is a result of violent video games, while Ferguson et al. (2008) give a different interpretation and believe that this research speaks little about actual tendency to violence, since respondents would not show that kind of signs of aggression outside the lab. A similar ambiguity of the results can be seen in the laboratory research in 2013 with high school students as participants. They were divided into two groups. One group played non-violent games such as pinball and manifold, and the second group played violent games Grand Theft Auto III and Grand Theft Auto San Andreas. Both groups were given sweets they were free to consume; however, the students were given a clear note that the candy was harmful to their health. The results of the research showed that the group playing violent games had eaten more sweets than the other group, which led scientists to conclude that violent games have a negative influence on student self-control (Nakaya, 2015).

But there are at least two alternative interpretations of these findings. The fact that one type of game has affected eating more sweets does not have to say anything about self-control. The first group playing a non-violent video game was playing a pinball, a game where constant alertness and concentration on the ball is required, as well as readiness to react if needed, or a minigolf that also requires high concentration, patience and calmness. On the other hand, a group playing violent video games played Grand Theft Auto series games. These games are dynamic, but require less concentration and more agility and speed, so they provide more excitement. The result is comparable to film-based research, where Tal, Zuckerman and Wansink (2014) came to the conclusion that the most food is eaten when watching action movies.

The second interpretation of this research may be reduced to the time available during game play which can be used for picking up candy. Pinball and manifold players will probably spend more time concentrating on the events than the Grand Theft Auto players, as it is almost always possible to take a break in the latter game. In 2011, Pediatrics published a study about video addiction issues. Participants were third, seventh and eighth grade students who were interviewed three times during a three-year period. This study is an example of a well-designed and conducted research, since the

same students were interviewed during a given period, allowing authors to observe certain regularity in the responses as well as tracking changes in that period.

According to the results, children who reported video games addiction were also more prone to anxiety and depression and they had poorer school success. Perhaps the most obvious problem about described study would be the readiness of the student to take the survey and their previous knowledge, so they might have responded similar to earlier

BOUNDARIES OF LEARNING FROM VIDEO GAMES

Learning from video games spans a wide area of topics, not all of which can be treated successfully under the same heading. Certainly, an awareness of the different sectional views that exist is important to understanding the field. We have to be careful not to confuse learning how to play video games and accidentally learning from video games with a targeted educational effort of video games.

The educational use of video games is characteristic in that the learning experience has a specific goal. There is little doubt that we can learn from video games (like any other activity in life), but the harder questions relating to who, what, where, why, and how quickly we learn are not readily solved. Unfortunately, many researchers still settle for examining whether we learn from video games, neglecting to examine whether the results from a video game differ from those of other activities in, for example, efficiency and requirements (for example the monumental work by Gee, 2003).

The lack of control groups in research set-ups demonstrates this vividly. In most studies, researchers examine the effect of a course which includes video games without making any comparison with a similar course without video games (e.g. Adams, 1998; Kafai & Neulight, 2005; Squire, 2004), although there are exceptions (e.g. Lieberman, 2001; Wiebe & Martin, 1994). Problems related to the use of control groups suggest that it is useful to look at alternative methods to experimental set-ups, e.g. ethnographic classroom research, cultural studies, and design-based research.

An important distinction when determining the educational use of video games is the different game titles used. The first, most obvious category, is commercial educational video games, often known as edutainment. Edutainment focuses on teaching the player certain specific skills: mostly algebra, spelling, problem-solving, and other basic skills. Edutainment titles

include Math Blaster, Pajama Sam and Castle of Dr. Brain. Edutainment titles have a strong educational component but often do not reflect the motivational drive of commercial titles (Facer et al., 2003; Leyland, 1996). The second category comprises commercial entertainment titles used fairly haphazardly for education. The educational goals of commercial video games are indirect rather than direct, goals that can lead to a skewed focus in the learning process. However, their strength is that the motivational part is well documented from success on the commercial entertainment market (Kirriemuir & McFarlane, 2002).

The third category is research-based educational video games; these often challenge the existing formula of edutainment. Edutainment originating from research often presents new approaches and has strong documentation for learning outcomes.

However, these titles often lack the budgets and technical quality to compete with the more commercial titles. They make a greater impact only if published on the commercial market with some modifications.

Exemplary titles are Oregon Trail, Logical Journey of the Zoombinis, Phoenix Quest and Global Conflicts: Palestine.

FINDINGS

- More than 90% of the populations under study play video games either themselves or their children or both.
- Almost 84% of the respondents under consideration play video games on a regular basis that is daily or weekly.
- More than 40% of their pendants under consideration, either themselves or their children play video games for entertainment purpose. 12% of the respondents under study either themselves or their children play video games in order to relieve their stress. 26% of the population under consideration play video games either themselves or their children to pass freetime. While the remaining 20% of the population under study play video games either themselves or their children to compete with friends.
- Around 48% of the population under consideration, either they or their children prefer action games and very few, that is, 16% prefer puzzle games or strategy games.
- 40% of the populations are of the view that video games have a negative impact on the players while 22% are of the view that video games have a positive impact on the players.
- Over 70% of the population under study are of the view that video games lead to aggressive

and violent behavior.

- About 56% of the respondents under consideration feel that video games lead to loss of productivity among the players, while 20% are unaware about any changes in the productivity level due to video gaming.
- Over 65% of the populations under study think that video games lead to health issues.
- 78% of the population under study, think that video games help to develop various skills

CONCLUSION

It is clear from the survey that the effect of video games on the children is both constructive and destructive. Video games can definitely lead to adverse effects on academic performance and health. It is significant to recognize the encouraging and damaging aspects of video games. Playing games by children communally as part of their balanced lifestyle generally provides positive effects. Some research has also shown that video games can also be helpful in terms of engaging students more in the learning process. This seems particularly factual in areas involving critical skills. They can contribute additional way of learning along with many other pedagogical methods which are presently popular. Students and educators must to be aware of the dangers of extreme gaming. It can have academic, societal, and transcendental consequences. Students have been known to completely disconnect from their friends and surroundings when playing games. As was shown by several statistics presented earlier a small percentage of children, spend a huge amount of time playing video games. Balance needs to be emphasized as an important part of the healthy lifestyle, and video games are no exception.

The different approaches to educational experiences with video games are largely not clear-cut when we encounter them in research, but instead are a mix. The different learning approaches clearly have something to offer on different levels especially when we have to develop edutainment that can work in the educational setting. The split between different titles adhering to behaviorism, cognitive, constructionism, or the socio-cultural does not suggest that one is bound to approach the titles exclusively from that angle. Rather, the categorization points to the underlying assumptions that the teacher can expand on.

RECOMMENDATIONS

After all I recommend the Students living Mogadishu to;

- No more than two hours per day of screen-based entertainment.
- Parents should create a “media plan” that dictates what hours a child can enjoy video game without affecting behavior and homework.
- They stimulate creativity, focus and visual memory. ...

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